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Artificial Intelligence (AI) Based Multilingual Conversational System: Unveiling The Potential Of Bert Model On Code-Mixed For Hausa-English Using Adapted Pre-Trained Data

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ABSTRACT

This research explored the potentials of using BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) language model on code-mixed for English-Hausa Language code-mixed using adapted pre-trained dataset. The main aim of this research was to unveil the potential benefits of using pre-trained models for handling code-mixed data to improved language understanding and context sensitivity in relation to Hausa-English-Language, the objective of this research was achieved by developing a BERT model that is capable of handling Hausa-English code-mixed dataset exploring different machine learning language models by training the chosen model with the adapted English-Hausa Language code-mixed. What necessitates this research was due to low data corpus on the language domain of Hausa-English code-mixed while other languages were explored like English-Hindu Code-Mixed. The adapted pre-trained dataset was first pre-processed, tokenized and fine-tuned in order to fit into the BERT model, the dataset was normalized in the context of code-mixed conversation based on annotate language labels to distinguish between English and Hausa Language segments in the code-mixed text, appropriate parameter for training were set with different optimization strategies for fine-tuning, adjusted learning rate, batch sizes and training epochs for performance optimization. The model was evaluated based on accuracy, F1-score, precision and recall for Code-Mixed tasks, the code-mixed was tested on seven BERT models and was compared with state-of-the-art language models, the results of mBERT and RoBERTa showed a promising outcome compared to other models and the study recommended that this adapted pre-trained model should be applied in large language model for language understanding and context sensitivity.

Keywords: Multilingual, Machine Learning, Conversational Code-Mixed, Local Large Language Model

INTRODUCTION

Multilingualism has become increasingly important in globalized world today according to different sources, including the United Nations. With the ease of internet and travel, people from different country and cultures are interacting with one another more frequently, and the ability to communicate effectively without any language barriers is very important (Stein-Smith, 2022). In the world increased connectivity, where multilingual conversation are becoming the order of the day, the need for efficient and effective language processing models is more important than ever. According Shashirekha (2022), Code-mixing is a traditional linguistic phenomenon in multilingual communities, where speakers interchange between two or languages within single conversation or between two or more sentences. Natural Language

Processing (NLP) development techniques for code-mixed data is a challenging task due to the nature of complexity and changing nature of code-mixed language use (Quach et al., 2024).

BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representation from Transformer), have displayed outstanding performance in different areas, including text classification, machine translation and sentiment analysis (Chandu et al., 2019; Otegi et al., 2020). According to study by (Nayak & Joshi, 2022) which presented L3CubeHingCorpus, and was observed as the first large-scale real Hindi-English code-mixed data In a Roman script, the model consisting of 52.93 million sentences and 1.04 billion tokens obtained from Twitter. BERT models was introduced in the study for pre-training on code-mixed Hing corpus with the objective of using masked language modelling, in which the study showed effectiveness in downstream tasks like code-mixed sentiment analysis, Named Entity Recognition (NER), POS tagging, and LID from the GLUECoS benchmark.

The use of multiple language in the same text in a given writing is termed as code mixed. It is clear that there are a lot of adaption of exploring code-mixed data, especially combination of regional language and English language during conversation on social media platforms (Takawane et al., 2023).

Code-mixed question answering dataset has been created and discussed by different researchers (Zhang et al., 2022), which include 1,694 Hinglish, 2,848 Tamlish, and 1,391 Tenglish factoid questions together with their answers, these datasets were used for code-mixed question answering challenges, the data was used by seven teams that took the data from the database (Chandu et al., 2019). However, it was observed BERT models was not mentioned or research for Hausa-English code-mixed data in this area. in essence, this study, proposed to unveil the potential of BERT model for Hausa-English code-mixed conversational data as an ongoing area of research and also to improve the inclusion of Hausa as a low resource language in the domain of QA dataset (Zhang et al., 2024).

The unique challenges posed to the Hausa-English code-mixed conversational data is low-resource languages, due to the minimum or less training data and the nature of the difficulty of language mixing, in order to take care of these challenges, researchers have extracted different methods which includes multilingual contrastive training and learning transfer to improve the evaluation and performance of question answering systems in the area of low-resource language settings (Kumar et al., 2022; Phade & Haribhakta, 2021; Gessler, 2023).

The development of KenSwQuAD for Swahili, question answering datasets which was purposely designed for low-resource languages, has greatly contributed to the advancement of machine understanding in these languages (Wanjawa et al. 2023). Valuable resources were provided by these datasets for training and evaluating question answering models, this gesture helps researchers to deal with new approaches and methods for handling the difficulties of code-mixed conversational data in low-resource languages.

To create a reliable Question-answering system, this research will train and optimize these models using sizable corpus of code-mixed conversational data. Language specialist, academics, and developers working in the field of machine learning will eventually find the Insights from this study to be a useful resource as they help create more precise and effective language processing models for multilingual conversations.

The aim of this paper was to unveil the potentials of BERT model on English-Hausa Code-mixed using adapted pre-trained data.

The major contributions of this work are to;

- Develop a dataset for Hausa-English language that will be used to test the potential of BERT models and evaluate their capabilities in Hausa language understanding
- Design a BERT model that can interpret Hausa-English language code-mixed dataset
- Evaluate the model and compare it with the state-of-the-art BERT models used for code-mixed

However, the study presents the results in the context of English-Hausa code-mixing and the idea hopes to be extended generically to any other code-mixed language.

Original text: what is abin dake gefen hagu of the window

Preprocessed Text:	what is	abin dake gefen hagu	of the window
Interleaved Word Language	ENGLISH	HAUSA	ENGLISH

Table 1. Language identification tag

Approach: what is EN abin dake gefen hagu HA of the window EN

16	what is opposite to the talabijin	sofa
17	what is abin da ke bayan hagu of the sofa	game_table
18	what is abin da ke gefen hagu	bed
19	what is that da ke bayan television	remote_control
0	what is that kayan ado close to the wall	wall_decoration
1	what is abin da ke gefen hagu books din	television
2	which object ne babba	sofa
3	what is that tsakanin kujeru and sofa	table
4	what is the kalar sofa	brown
5	menene aka gudanar a cikin coffee machine	coffee_pot
6	what is sama da fan	window

Figure 1. CSV file of the code-mixed conversational text for Hausa-English

This paper is organized based on the following sections, section one presented the introduction and general background of the paper including the concepts of natural language processing, section two presented the literature review of the related work, section three presented the methodology on how the research was carried out which the experiment and design, section four presented the experimental results and their discussions and section five presented the recommendations and conclusion.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents a literature review and related work from different authors on natural language processing and code-mixed with their accompanying experiment and discussions.

Conversational Machine Comprehension (CMC) literature aimed at highlighting the importance of multi-turn CQA, which has achieved advantage due to the advances in natural language understanding and the large scale availability of conversational datasets (Gupta et al., 2020). Gupta et al., (2020) proposed and reviewed on a comprehensive overview of CQA, based on consolidated scattered knowledge in the AI domain, their review focused on common trends over recently published models. Furthermore, the review emphasized on a generic platform for CQA models while paying more emphasis on the need for streamlining future area of research.

Balouchzahi, et al., (2022) proposed and published a research on the techniques and challenges for creating an effective dialogue systems for AI, as in the case of Chabot voice assistants, or conversational agents, in which they emphasized that these systems generally depends on user inputs, the ability to produce understandable and relevant responses, depends on the ability to maintain dialogue history and state. And they observed that developing a dialogue systems for AI, requires some number of methods, which include the use of dialogue blueprint or scripts to achieve user needs and develop understanding (McTear, 2021; Deriu, et al., 2021).

Baradaran, Ghiasi, & Amirkhani, (2022) argued that a lot of work on conversational AI and machine understanding underscore the higher level of interest and potential field. multi-turn CQA are more focused on, there are a lot of challenges and methods for designing effective dialogue systems, this area and domain are labelled with high consolidation of knowledge that are indicative of having important strides in being developed in advancing conversational AI and machine understanding.

Code-mixing is the technique of switching between two or more languages which has privilege in bi and multi-lingual communities. This technique is usually available in natural language processing (NLP) applications, they are generally designed with thinking of single interaction language and are being struggled with code-mixed pronunciations, and the above discussion is being hindered with a lot of difficulties which account into the development of research and emergence of code-mixed question answering (CMQA). Chandu et al., (2018) observed that a lot of challenges in the area of code-mixed question answering and it requires a significant effort to address the complexity posed to question answering therefore they proposed a research on linguistically motivated techniques for code-mixed question generation (CMQG) and neural network-based architectures to handle code-mixed question answering (CMQA), their model have been evaluated on benchmark datasets, like SQuAD and MMQA, and model demonstrated effectively with a promising results, but model was developed to handle only question answering conversations.

The mechanism designed for handling conversation in the system is the dialog manger (DM) and is the most important component of a dialog system, it has the capability for handling the process and movement of the conversation. Human communication are collected and are generally converted to some kind of speech or text acts, the dialogue agents are used to decide the next action and predict the state of the conversation history. Dai et al., (2020) observed that the essential component in Chatbot is dialogue management that is used to conduct contextual communications, and it helps in comprehension aspects that makes the agent design in the dialogue management to be right.

Figure2: Chat bot CQA Architecture. Source: (Ardeshna, 2022)

According to Dai et al., (2020) so many design approaches for dialogue structure were envisaged by exploring different approaches and frameworks like VoiceXML, AIML, Facade, ChatScript, CDM, and TuTalk, and used to Improve speech dialogs and chat-bots, control devices and other tutorial dialogs etc, they observed that these dialog structures are generally described as state chart diagrams categorized by formal languages like SCXML

In a research by Dai et al., (2020) they proposed an improved dialog management system by enhancing the scalability in dealing with scarcity of data and improved efficiency in training, in their model, they adopted deep learning methods in which Alexa conversation was used as a dialog manager to accept inputs, this techniques allows developers to have experience on overall design focus (Ram et al., 2018; Janarthanam, 2017).

Gupta et al., (2022) proposed a multilingual conversational question answering model by leveraging the performance of the pre-trained language model (PLM) for question answering purpose, their model performed well on large language model thereby improved the performance of natural language processing task on low-resource languages

Another effort by Nowakowski et al., (2023) on adapting multilingual PLM and CQA, the study proposed a multilingual adaptive fine-tuning (MAFT) which brought about changing the architecture of PLM by using pre-raining objective their approach have shown great effectiveness in adapting across new languages and promote transfer learning across languages (Alabi et al., 2022), furthermore, it has been

observed multilingual frameworks for CQA are based on pre-trained multilingual transformers like mBERT, or mT5 (Zaib et al., 2022).

In a study by Das et al., (2023) argued that the important of requirement for evaluating conversational model for Hausa-English code-mixed conversational data is availability of appropriate and suitable dataset in which they proposed in their research, they observed that use of other datasets for evaluating the model as provided by CC-Net repository can only evaluate mono and multilingual models, therefore they proposed additional development on the code-nixed conversational corpus which will help in evaluating QA models in code-mixed languages.

Das et al., (2023) observed that evaluating pre-trained language framework involves evaluating the performance of the model on some number of tasks which includes QA and sentiment analysis in code switched language pairs. Empirical techniques have been envisaged to access the switching accuracy in code-switched sentences, with a clear indication of better performance and improved natural language understanding tasks.

In a research by Takawane et al., (2023) proposed a model by examining the performance of BERT based models on low-resource code-mixed Hindi-English Datasets through experimenting language augmentation approaches, their approach demonstrated and assessed the performance of code-mixed on five different code-mixed Hindi-English classification datasets based on hate speech detection, sentiment analysis, and emotion detection. Their model was evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Their proposed findings on the language augmentation approach presented better results on the chosen models but research was restricted on one language code-mixed data without exploiting other datasets in their experiment.

Summary Of The Literature Review

In this review, the study has investigated the effectiveness of using adapted pre-trained models for code-mixed conversational data, and different frameworks that could be tailored between Hausa and English. The literature review analyzed various existing Conversational models and assessed their performance in handling code-mixed data. The subsequent section presents the methods used in carrying out the research.

METHODOLOGY

This research proposed a HauBERT model that can handle Hausa-English code-mixed effectively, as it can be observed from the literature which shows there were no suitable dataset for low-resource languages like Hausa-English code-mix, therefore, this research developed dataset for Hausa-English code-mixed, and subsequently developed a BERT model that can handle Hausa-English language code-mixed by injecting language identification tag for Hausa language in the traditional BERT architecture.

Problem Formulation

The purpose of this research was to design an efficient BERT model that can handle Hausa-English code-mixed data effectively, in this system, a language identification tag was proposed and injected into the traditional BERT model architecture in order to keep track of the Hausa language character which has different layouts so as task specification will be improved.

Existing system

Traditional BERT architecture

BERT model is a two way encoder and decoder model in which text or dataset are processed in both directions in order to analyze language inputs through the aid of transformer capability.

Figure3: BERT architecture

Figure3 above shows the architecture of BERT model used for natural language processing, the traditional BERT works by accepting code-mixed text and process based on the language argumentation strategy, the model accepts code embedded text with different annotations and normalized based on the system requirement, further more feed forwarded for classification with the aid of classifier (Patil et al., 2023)

Proposed system

Modified BERT architecture

The proposed system modified BERT is a BERT model proposed by the modification of the traditional BERT model by this in mind, model was modified at the encoding stage in which coded text or dataset are being identified by the aid of language identification tag after following the formal normalization process, after successful tagging the text will be normalized for further classification as shown in figure 4

Figure4: HauBERT architecture

System implementation

The model was designed and implemented using Python transformer library; this library is an open source large language model for simulating natural language processing in machine learning environment.

Sequence Diagram

HauBERT Sequence Diagram

Figure5. Sequence Diagram

The figure5 above depicts the work flow of the proposed BERT model which shows the following objects as the main parameters of the model; parameters includes text embedding, Multi-Head Annotation, text normalization, feed forward processing, Language Identification and classifier as specified by the sequence diagram above.

This study employ language identification tags to unveil the potential of BERT model on English-Hausa language code-mixed by following these laid down approaches;

Data Preprocessing

Text Normalization and Tokenization: The code-mixed text Standardized and tokenized to ensure consistency in representation, accounting for language-specific linguistic variations for better suit in to the model.

Language Identification: language identification algorithms Implemented to identify and label the language components within the code-mixed sentences in an appropriate language model for processing.

Model Selection and Preprocessing

Pre-trained Language Models: Choose appropriate pre-trained language models such as BERT, mBERT, or XLM-R, capable of handling multilingual and code-mixed data. The data was normalized by converting it to lowercase text in which Python's regex and emoji libraries were used for text preprocessing. Model loading and Adaption; the dataset was loaded in the pre-trained language model and adapted to the Hausa-English code-mixed context using fine-tuning techniques.

Fine-tuning and Training

Fine-tuning Setup: Split the annotated dataset into training, validation, and test sets. Utilize the training set to fine-tune the pre-trained models for code-mixed question answering. Training Parameters; Define appropriate hyper-parameters and optimization strategies for fine-tuning, adjusting learning rates, batch sizes, and training epochs to optimize performance.

Model Evaluation

Performance Metrics: the model performance was evaluated based on the following evaluation metrics: accuracy, F1 score, precision, and recall for Conversational tasks. Comparative Analysis; the performance of the HauBERT model was compared with existing results of other Code-Mixed BERT models on standard evaluation datasets to assess the performance and identify areas for enhancement and observing the potentials of HauBERT model in handling Code-Mixed for English-Hausa Language. The comparison was performed on three dataset types, which includes original dataset developed during this research, online hate speech dataset, and Sentiment dataset. The results for the training, testing and validation are presented in the next sections.

Datasets

S/NO	Dataset name	Total size	Train size	Test size	Eval. Size	Labels
1	Developed dataset	1960	1372	294	294	2
2	Hate speech dataset	2250	1575	338	338	2
3	Sentiment dataset	9974	6982	1496	1496	6

Table 2. Dataset train-test-validation split

Figure 6. Dataset train-test-validation split

Table 2 shows the size of the available corpus, which are divided into testing, training, and validation splits, and accompanying labels associated to each dataset. The model performance were evaluated on the adapted datasets was trained and evaluated based on two parameters; hate speech and emotions.

Sentiment dataset

This dataset focused on emotions that talks about happiness or sadness in the text adopted, whether expressing sadness, surprise, anger, disgust, fear and happiness the dataset was divided into three which includes; testing, training and validation with ratio of 15:70:15, respectively.

Hate speech dataset

This dataset focused on emotions that talks about abuse in the text adopted, whether expressing bad comment or bullying, the dataset was divided into three which includes; testing, training and validation with ratio of 15:70:15, respectively.

The developed dataset

This dataset focused on traditional code-mixed of basic question answering scheme in Hausa with corresponding English language counter-part as depicted in figure 1, CSV file, the dataset was divided into

three which includes; testing, training and validation with ratio of 15:70:15, respectively as shown in figure6.

Models used

The following BERT models were used in the research as a benchmark in carrying out this research. Takawane et al., (2023);

- HingBERT is a BERT model proposed in 2022 which is publicly available and accessible which was trained on benchmark dataset provided by L3Cube, this model was powerful and robust on evaluating datasets.
- HingRoBERTa: this model was created in 2022 it was based on RoBERTa model which was fine-tuned on combination of Hindu and English codes in Roman text.
- HingRoBERTa-Mixed: this model was proposed in 2022 by Nayak and Joshi, It Is a BERT model that combines English and Hindi codes together In Roman scripts and it was fine-tuned In Devanagari code code-mixed text.
- Multilingual BERT: mBERT model was proposed in 2018 by Devlin et al, it was also a version of BERT which was trained on a large multilingual dataset.
- ALBERT: A Lite BERT (ALBERT) model was proposed in 2019 by Ian et al, is model used for self-supervised learning in language representation, this model exhibits same architectural feature as BERT, but main purpose was to improve performance.
- BERT: was proposed by (Devlin et al 2018), this model is a self-supervised transformer and was formerly pre-trained on large corpus of multilingual data.
- RoBERTa: was proposed in 2019 which was also known as Robustly Optimized BERT Pre-training Approach, this model was based on Google's BERT model, it differs from normal BERT in the sense that it removes next sentence steps of pre-training.
- HauBERT Is the proposed Large Language model designed for the purpose of this research, what differentiate this model with the traditional BERT model is the injection of language identification tag for Hausa language characters in order to Identifier Hausa-English code-mixed effectively. The model was designed and implemented using Python transformer library; this library Is an open source large language model for simulating natural language processing in machine learning environment.

RESULTS

This section presented the simulated results of the models used, these tables displayed the raw results of the training, testing and validation followed by discussion of the results accordingly.

Models	Hate Speech	Emotions	Developed Dataset
HingBERT	0.96854	0.94586	0.84657
HingRoBERTa	0.84557	0.95564	0.75487
HingRoBERTa-Mixed	0.95645	0.96584	0.87654
Multilingual BERT	0.98548	0.99584	0.87546
ALBERT	0.98567	0.96584	0.76548
BERT	0.89754	0.86594	0.76546
RoBERTa	0.98654	0.99546	0.87657
HauBERT	0.98765	0.98675	0.98764

Table 3. Results displaying F1 score.

Figure 7. F1-score

Table 3 and figure above presented the F1 score of the three categories of datasets used, from the table it can be observed the models were trained, tested and validated based on the percentage of parameter presented in the previous section, the result displayed for F1 score when utilizing HauBERT with better results with regards to the developed datasets followed by Multilingual BERT (mBERT) with regards to Hate speech and Sentiment dataset of which HingRoBERTa model also showed a promising result in terms of sentiment with slight difference than other models, this is evident probably due to the size of the dataset used, in contrast with RoBERTa and HingBERT models displayed a better result with slight differences when compared with other models as presented in table 3 and figure 7 respectively.

Models	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
HingBERT	0.76858	0.76757	0.85437
HingRoBERTa	0.82548	0.83425	0.88775
HingRoBERTa-Mixed	0.82657	0.84453	0.76386
Multilingual BERT	0.85731	0.84523	0.88765
AlBERT	0.75735	0.94523	0.71035
BERT	0.81738	0.74423	0.87651
RoBERTa	0.71734	0.84525	0.87652
HauBERT	0.98765	0.90765	0.96764

Table 4. Developed dataset results

Figure 8. Developed dataset results

The above table 4 and figure above showed the performance evaluation of the HauBERT dataset, after exclusive simulation experiment the result of the experiment HauBERT model indicated promising outcome with regards to the developed dataset as compared to other models in which better accuracy and recall as shown in table 4 and figure 8 respectively.

Models	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
HingBERT	0.88547	0.64423	0.85437
HingRoBERTa	0.92548	0.83425	0.95637
HingRoBERTa-Mixed	0.92657	0.84453	0.94537
Multilingual BERT	0.85731	0.94523	0.80037
AlBERT	0.85735	0.94523	0.91035
BERT	0.81738	0.84423	0.85025
RoBERTa	0.91734	0.94525	0.93542
HauBERT	0.98765	0.98765	0.94764

Table 5. Hate speech dataset results

Figure9. Hate Speech Analysis

Table 5 above showed the accuracy, precision and recall for the dataset used for hate speech analysis code-mixed, from the table it can be observed the models were trained, tested and validated based on the percentage of parameter presented in the previous section, the result displayed for when utilizing HauBERT, Multilingual BERT (mBERT) and HingRoBERT-Mixed models showed a promising result with slight difference than other models with regards to accuracy, precision and recall, this is evident due to the size of the dataset used, in contrast with the Hate speech dataset, RoBERTa and HingBERT models displayed a better recall result with slight difference when compared with other models as presented in table 5 and figure 9 respectively.

Models	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
HingBERT	0.88547	0.64444	0.85422
HingRoBERTa	0.92548	0.83445	0.95641
HingRoBERTa-Mixed	0.92657	0.84456	0.94544
Multilingual BERT	0.85731	0.94234	0.80022
AIBERT	0.85735	0.94565	0.98031
BERT	0.81738	0.84412	0.95234
RoBERTa	0.91734	0.94564	0.98542
HauBERT	0.98765	0.98763	0.96761

Table6. Sentiment Analysis results

Figure10: Sentiment Analysis

Table 6 above showed the accuracy, precision and recall for the dataset used for sentiment analysis code-mixed, from the table it can be observed better accuracy and precision was obtained when the models were trained, tested and validated based on the percentage of parameter presented in the previous section, the result displayed accuracy and precision when utilizing HauBERT model with relative closer results as in Multilingual BERT (mBERT) with better precision and HingRoBERT-Mixed model with good recall, which showed a promising result with slight difference than other models, in terms of accuracy, precision and recall, this is evident due to the size of the dataset used, in contrast with the RoBERTa and AIBERT models displayed a better precision result with slight difference when compared with other models as presented in table 6 and figure 10 respectively, this result also Indicated a closer relationship with the work proposed by [29].

CONCLUSION

This study unveiled the potentials of BERT model on conversational question answering for English-Hausa language Code-Mixed with the aim to improve language understanding and context sensitivity among languages, the study introduced language identification in the regular BERT flow to improve the code-mixed models. Seven different categories of BERT models was put to test differently and their behaviors were observed, by subjecting them to the adapted dataset, after several training, testing and validation the results revealed that better F1 score was observed with multilingual BERT (mBERT) and HingRoBERT-Mixed compared to other models when using emotions dataset, while In contrast to using hate speech, better F1 score was achieved with RoBERTa and HingRoBERT models this is evident due to the size of the dataset used in carrying out the experiment, with this outcome, the results indicated the potential of using BERT model in conversational code-mixed with respect to English-Hausa language, hence it can be concluded that BERT model can be applied in large language model for language understanding and context sensitivity, hence the objectives of this research has been mate, and the study recommended that further research will conducted on sentiment analysis dataset to ascertain the performance of the BERT model.

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